

Perceived Organizational Support as Predictor of the Three Components of Organizational Commitment

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Abstract: - The objective of this research was to determine the effect of perceived organizational support on the three components of organizational commitment. Primary data through survey questionnaire was collected from the college teachers of Sindh Province Pakistan. Through the empirical investigation of the data it was found that college teachers perceived support from their organization and they were committed to their organization. Perceived organizational support was found to have significant effect on the affective, continuance and normative commitment of the teachers. However the effect of perceived organizational support on normative commitment was lesser than its effect on affective and continuance commitment. This study contributed to determine the effect of perceived organizational support on the commitment level of the college teachers in context of Pakistan. The implications of the results are discussed.

Key Words: Perceived Organizational support, Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, Normative Commitment

1.0 Introduction

Every organization wants the employees who are knowledgeable, experienced, skilful, supporting and so on. But this is the world of give & take. It's a reciprocal process. If an organization has made itself ready for supporting the talent of their employees, willing to support them to meet their current as well as future needs and valuing the efforts of their employees then it is likely that employee would perceive organizational support which in turn would create the organizational commitment of the employees. A great organization do needs the same support on part of their employees but that is only possible when employees are committed to do so.

Relationship between the perceived organizational support and organizational commitment has been studied by many researchers and they have found the significant effect of perceived organizational support on various components of organisational commitment. Particularly positive and significant relationship is found between perceived organizational support and affective components of organizational commitment. In context of Pakistan a little attention has been given to this issue. This research has taken an initiative to determine the existence of perceived organizational support and three components of organizational commitment in the teachers of the colleges of the two districts namely: Sukkur and Khairpur Mir's, of the Sindh province of Pakistan.

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2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Background

2.1.1 Perceived organizational support

In general sense support is described as the encouragement, backing, help or assistance. Even in day to day routine activities we need support to do work effectively and efficiently. When it comes to organizations, it becomes very crucial for employees working in any organization to get the support on part of their organizations. If employees feel that there is an organization that cares about them, about their work and there is a value for their work in the organization then it is likely that it will create a perception of organizational support in the minds of employees. Realising the importance of perceived organizational support many organizations, researchers started to work on the employee's perception of perceived organizational support. In the early study on perceived organizational support, conducted by Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, and Sowa (1986), perceived organizational support is described as, "Employees in an organization form global beliefs concerning the extent to which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being". Levison H. (1965) describes that there is a process of reciprocation between an employee and organization. There are mutual expectations between organization and an employee. When this process of mutual expectations is working well then an employee perceives psychologically support on part of the organization and which improves organizational functioning. Thus perceived organizational support is the pre-requisite for creating any psychological state in the mind of employees. Once an employee perceives organizational support then it is likely that it will lead towards the creation of various outcomes. One of the strongest outcomes created by perceived organizational support is organizational commitment.

2.1.2 Organizational Commitment

Due to its broader sense lot of definitions has been given for organizational commitment. Bateman and Strasser(1984) defines organizational commitment as "multidimensional in nature, involving an employee's loyalty to the organization, willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization, degree of goal and value congruency with the organization, and desire to maintain membership" (p.95). Dictionary of business and management defines organizational commitment as, "An individual's psychological attachment to an organization and desire to remain part of it". Initially Meyer & Allen (1984) suggested two dimensions of organizational commitment: Affective and continuance commitment. Later Allen & Meyer (1990) suggested a third dimension: normative commitment. They describe these dimensions as:

2.1.3 Affective Commitment

Affective commitment is literally being part of organizational commitment. Affective commitment is described as "Employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organization".

2.1.4 Continuance Commitment

"The extent to which employees feel committed to their organization by virtue of the costs that they feel are associated with leaving".

2.1.5 Normative commitment

“Employee’s feeling of perceived obligation to remain in the organization”.

3.0 Empirical Evidence on relationship between perceived organizational Support and Organizational Commitment and Hypotheses

Yuanqing He, Kin Keung Lai, Yagang Lu (2011) studied the effect of organizational support on employee’s commitment in hotel industry of China. They found that among various dimensions of organizational support namely managerial support has the greatest influence of employee’s commitment. Secondly co-worker relationship had positive influence on affective commitment. Role ambiguity could not be proved as predictor of affective commitment.

Nasrin Arshadia (2011) found that in employees of an industrial organization of Iran, perceived organizational support was positively related to organizational commitment and negatively related to turnover intention.

Lynn McFarlane Shore and Sandy J. Wayne (1993) found positive and significant relationship between perceived organizational support and AC; however they found negative insignificant relationship between perceived organizational support and continuance commitment.

Rhoades, L., & Eisenberger, R. (2002) conducted the Meta analysis of 70 studies of different researchers and found that perceived organizational support has strong and positive effect on AC while perceived organizational support was found to have a small negative relationship with continuance commitment. Moreover it was found that perceived organizational support has a significant effect on turnover intention of the employees.

Meyer et. al. (2002) also conducted the Meta analysis of 155 studies. Their focus was to determine the antecedents, correlates and consequences of various dimensions of organizational commitment. Their findings related to this research were that, correlations between the three dimensions of commitment namely, affective, normative, continuance, were negative. Among these three dimensions, affective commitment had strong negative relationship with turnover cognition followed by normative and continuance commitment.

Linda et al. (2001) found that for two year sample data, perceived organizational support was positively related to temporal change in AC but AC was not associated with temporal change in perceived organizational support. Similar results were found for three year sample data. Thus in this study it was proved that perceived organizational support leads toward AC

Tek -Yew Lew (2009) found that in contrary to many studies perceived organizational support does not have a significant direct effect on turnover of the employees but perceived organizational support does have a direct significant effect on AC of the employees. However AC also significantly reduces turnover intention of employees. Thus findings of their research suggest that employee who were higher on perceived organizational support, showed stronger AC and in turn they were less likely to leave the organization.

Godfrey Tumwesigye (2010) and Darolia et al. (2010) found that perceived organizational support is positively and significantly related to all three components of organizational commitment.

Makanjee et al. (2006) determined the relationship between the antecedents of perceived organizational support and three components of organizational commitment. They found positive and significant relationship between antecedents of perceived organizational support and three components of organizational commitment.

Overall majority of the researchers have found positive and significant relationship between the perceived organizational support and affective organizational commitment but in case of relationship between perceived organizational support and continuance commitment some researchers have found no relationship and negative relationship between perceived organizational support and continuance commitment while some researchers have also found positive and significant relationship between perceived organizational support and continuance commitment. Thus above literature review provides us basis to hypothesize positive and significant relationship between perceived organizational support and affective commitment while due to mixed results for perceived organizational support and continuance commitment it is hypothesized that there will be significant relationship between perceived organizational support and continuance commitment but the direction of relationship is left to the results of this research. Relationship between perceived organizational support and normative commitment has been studied by a few and they have found significant and positive relationship between perceived organizational support and normative commitment. Due to little research on relationship between perceived organizational support and normative commitment it is hypothesized that there will be significant relationship between perceived organizational support and normative commitment but the direction of relationship is again left to the results of this research.

Hypothesis 1: Perceived organizational support has a positive effect on affective organizational commitment

Hypothesis 2: Perceived organizational support has a significant effect on continuance Organizational Commitment

Hypothesis 3: Perceived organizational support has a significant effect on normative organizational Commitment

4.0 Research Design

4.1 Sample

The Data was collected from the college teachers of two districts of Sindh province of Pakistan. The data was collected from only the male teachers because researcher could not get access to female teachers of the colleges. Originally around 260 questionnaires were distributed and 203 properly filled questionnaires returned by the respondents, which makes a healthy response rate of around 78 percent.

4.1.2 Measures

4.1.2.1 Perceived organizational support

Perceived organizational support is measured by a seven point liker scale, 08 item survey questionnaire originally developed by Robert Eisenberger, Jim Cummings, Stephen Armeli, and Patrick Lynch (1997). This instrument is most commonly used by many researchers for measuring the perceived organizational support.

4.1.2.2 Organizational Commitment

Three components of Organizational Commitment namely, affective, continuance, and normative commitment are measured by a seven point likert scale, 06 item questionnaire for each component of organizational commitment, originally developed by Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., &

Smith, C. A. (1993). This instrument is also most commonly used by many researchers for measuring the organizational commitment.

4.1.2.3 Analysis Techniques used in the Research

The unit of analysis in this research is an individual. Firstly preliminary data screening tests, normality tests are performed and scale's reliability is also checked. The data is analysed in two stages. Firstly the descriptive statistical techniques such as Arithmetic mean, Standard Deviation is determined. To check the strength of linear association between the independent variable and dependant variable, Correlation among all the variables are determined. In the second stage multiple regressions are run to determine the effect of perceived organizational support on three components of organizational commitment.

5.0 Results

5.1 Demographics Analysis

The demographic analysis results for gender showed that all the respondents were male. The age group analysis results showed that 29 percent of the respondents were between the age group of 20 to 29 years, 45 percent of the respondents were between age group of 30 to 39 years, 17 percent were between age group of 40 to 49 years and 09 percent were between age group of 50 and above. The education level analysis showed that 92 percent of the respondents had the 16 years of education, and 08 percent had 18 years (MS/M.Phil) of education. The job title analysis results showed that around 58 percent of the teachers were lecturers, around 36percent were assistant professors, and around 06 percent were associate professors.

5.2 Descriptive Analysis, Normality Tests, Reliability of Scales, and Common Method Variance

Preliminary data screening tests showed no missing value or aberrant values. For checking the normality of the data, the descriptive analysis results showed the skewness and kurtosis above the range of normality for many items. The result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic was also significant which suggests the abnormality of the data but this is common in primary data and this risk is avoided with a reasonably large sample of data usually 200+ (Tabachnick & Fidell 1996, p. 73). This research has a sample of above 200 so it would not affect the analysis process. Moreover the shapes of normality graphs (Histogram, Q-Q plots and box plots) suggesting that the data is reasonably normal. Few outliers were also detected in the normality analyses which were adjusted to mean values before analysis. In order to handle the issue of common method variance, Harman's single factor test procedure was adopted. According to Harman's single factor test, common method variance issue can be identified through exploratory factor analysis. If there is common method variance in the data then a single factor should emerge in the EFA or one factor should account for the maximum amount of variance (Podsakoff et al., 2003). In order to check the common method variance EFA of all the item was conducted and one factor solution accounted for less than 28 percent of the variance.

Descriptive analysis results showed that perceived organizational support has a mean of 5.211, Affective commitment has mean of 5.321, continuance commitment has mean of 4.769, and normative commitment showed mean result of 5.270. The reliability of scales adopted in this study was determined through Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability analysis results showed that perceived organizational support scale has a reliability of .820, affective commitment scale has

reliability of .681, continuance commitment scale has reliability of .781, and normative commitment scale has a reliability of .754. These results are given in table 01.

5.3 Correlational Analysis

Correlation between perceived organizational support and affective commitment was .588, between perceived organizational support and continuance commitment was .581, and between perceived organizational support and normative commitment it was .481. The correlation results are given in table 02.

5.4 Regression Analysis

5.4.1 Perceived Organizational Support and Affective Commitment

Regression analysis results showed that perceived organizational support has a significant effect on the affective commitment of the college teachers. Perceived organizational support explained 34 percent of variance in affective commitment. The beta coefficient result showed that one unit change in perceived organizational support results in .61 units change in affective commitment of the college teachers. These results are given in table 03.

5.4.2 Perceived Organizational Support and Continuance Commitment

These results showed that perceived organizational support has a significant effect on the continuance commitment of the college teachers. Perceived organizational support explained around 33 percent of variance in continuance commitment. The beta coefficient result showed that one unit change in perceived organizational support results in .65 units change in continuance commitment of the college teachers. These results are given in table 04.

5.4.3 Perceived Organizational Support and Normative Commitment

These results showed that perceived organizational support also has a significant effect on the normative commitment of the college teachers. Perceived organizational support explained around 18 percent of variance in normative commitment. The beta coefficient result showed that one unit change in perceived organizational support results in .486 units change in normative commitment of the college teachers. These results are given in table 05.

5.5 Discussion

The preliminary data screening analysis showed no existence of the missing or aberrant values because researcher checked all the questionnaires at the time of collecting from respondents and requested the respondents to refill the missing/ aberrant items properly.

Cronbach's alpha values showed the reliability of the measurement scales well above the acceptable level. The descriptive analysis mean values showed that the teachers of colleges agreed to perceive the support from the organization and mean results also showed the existence of all the three components of organizational commitment. However the mean value of affective commitment was higher than continuance and normative commitment which is consistent with the previous research. The correlational analysis showed the positive and significant relationship between perceived organizational support and all three components of organizational commitment. However the relationship between perceived organizational support and affective

commitment was a little more than relationship between perceived organizational support and continuance commitment. Relationship between perceived organizational support and normative commitment was less than the two other components. The regression analysis results also showed the significant effect of perceived organizational support on all three components of organizational commitment but the effect of perceived organizational support on normative commitment was less than the affective and continuance commitment. Thus correlation and regressions results supported our all three hypotheses of the positive and significant relationship between the perceived organizational support and all three components of organizational commitment.

Overall through this study it was determined that the college teachers of the Sindh province of Pakistan perceived the support from their organization and this support increases their commitment to the work significantly. At college education level teachers are receiving handsome amount of salary packages, more than sufficient number of official holidays, teachers can work part time in other institutions as well, and Education department assigns supervisors (Principals of colleges) within from the teachers. The workload on teachers is also adequate and teachers do enjoy task autonomy. Due to all these factors college level teachers have perceived a sufficient amount of organizational support which in turn increases their commitment to organization. The affective commitment results showed that teachers were found to be emotionally attached to their organization and they proudly identify themselves as part of college education. Teacher's continuance commitment level was also significant because in a country like Pakistan where there is huge unemployment if any person is getting a job like teacher, he or she thinks about it as a plum opportunity of their life. More over significant normative commitment results also showed that teachers ethically think that they should be committed to an organization where they perceive a sufficient amount of organizational support. Thus concluding this research as a useful step through which we determined the organizational support level and commitment level of the college teachers.

6.0 Managerial Implications

Through this study we contributed by highlighting the role of varying effect of perceived organizational support in enhancing employees' three commitment levels (i.e., affective, continuance, normative). The committed employees are the productive employees. This study established that the support provided by the organization can be very helpful to induce employees' commitment level either affective, continuance or normative. When an organization is supporting the talent of their employees, willing to support them to meet their current as well as future needs and valuing the efforts of their employees then such support is likely to increase the emotional attachment, the obligation to remain with the organization and the feeling that the value of such support is good enough to continuously remain committed to their organization.

7.0 Limitations

This research is not free of limitations such as:

The data used in this study was cross sectional which may create the common method variance problem.

The sample was limited to the male respondents of public sector colleges only.

This research included only one variable to predict the organizational commitment of the teachers while many other variables such as perceived supervisory support, job satisfaction etc., may have significant effect on the organizational commitment of the teachers.

8.0 Recommendations /Future Directions

It is recommended that female sample of respondent and private sector colleges may also be included in future research.

Perceived supervisory support may moderate the relationship between the perceived organizational support and organizational commitment. So it would be useful to determine the interactive effect of perceived organisational support and supervisory support on the organizational commitment of the teachers.

For more generalizable results this research may be expanded to the other areas of Pakistan as well.

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Appendix A

Table 01: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability

	Mean	St. Deviation	Alpha Coefficient
Perceived Organizational Support	5.211	.749	.820
Affective commitment	5.321	.780	.681
Continuance Commitment	4.769	.846	.781
Normative Commitment	5.270	.859	.754

Table 02: Correlation Matrix

	1	2	3	4
1. Perceived Organizational Support I				
2. Affective commitment	.588**	1		
3. Continuance Commitment	.581**	.394**	1	
4. Normative Commitment	.424**	.605**	.293**	1

** Correlations are significant at 0.01 levels

Table 03: Linear Regression Results for the Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Affective Commitment

Model Summary

R	R – Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.588	.345	.342	.633

Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Organizational Support

Coefficients

Independent Variable	β (Un.Std.)	Std. Error	β (Std.)	t	p
Perceived Organizational Support	.612	.059	.588	10.30	.00

Dependent Variable: Affective Commitment
 F – Value: 106.089
 Significance level: ** =.00

Table 04: Linear Regression Results for the Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Continuance Commitment

Model Summary

R	R – Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.581	.338	.334	.690

Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Organizational Support

Coefficients

Independent Variable	β (Un.Std.)	Std. Error	β (Std.)	t	p
Perceived Organizational Support	.656	.065	.581	10.126	.00

Dependent Variable: Continuance Commitment
 F – Value: 102.528
 Significance level: ** =.00

Table 05: Linear Regression Results for the Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Normative Commitment

Model Summary

R	R – Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.424	.180	.176	.780

Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Organizational Support

Coefficients

Independent Variable	β (Un.Std.)	Std. Error	β (Std.)	t	p
Perceived Organizational Support	.486	.073	.424	6.638	.00

Dependent Variable: Normative Commitment
 F – Value: 44.06
 Significance level: ** =.00